

HISTORY OF TELEVISION AND RADIO IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

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Annotation: This article provides information on the history of television and radio in Karakalpakstan. The concept of television was the work of many individuals in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, with its roots initially starting from back even in the 18th century. The first practical transmissions of moving images over a radio system used mechanical rotating perforated disks to scan a scene into a time-varying signal that could be reconstructed at a receiver back into an approximation of the original image. Development of television was interrupted by the Second World War. After the end of the war, all-electronic methods of scanning and displaying images became standard. Several different standards for addition of color to transmitted images were developed with different regions using technically incompatible signal standards. Television broadcasting expanded rapidly after World War II, becoming an important mass medium for advertising, propaganda, and entertainment.

Key words: television, radio, analog and digital formats, TV station, broadcasting, ether, Tv animations.

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Today, the television and radio industry is widely developed in our country. The first Karakalpak television program aired on November 5, 1964. Initially, "Tele janaliq" was prepared in 5 minutes in Russian and Karakalpak languages. Beginning in May 1965, Karakalpakstan's television broadcasts were extended from 2 hours to 2.5 hours and aired four times a week. From January 1, 1966, the broadcasts were extended to 3 hours and aired every day of the week except Wednesday. At the same time, on weekends and holidays, starting from 12.00, children's programs "Jetkinshek bizde qonaqta", "Miyneq batirliqti qaleydi", "Baliqshi balalar", "Shayirlar balalarga" have been shown. On November 29, 1966, the decision "On measures for the further development of television in Karakalpakstan" was adopted. In 1968, a mobile station (PTS) was acquired, making it possible to prepare shows outside the studio. In 1992, the country was renamed the Television and Radio Broadcasting Company, and in 2002 it was renamed the Republic of Karakalpakstan Television and Radio Company. For the first time this year, on June 1, the program "Assalawma aleykum, Karakalpakstan" was aired. [1:78]

During the years of independence, the activities of the Karakalpakstan TV channel have changed radically. Amazing new genre shows and TV shows have been created. Today, Karakalpakstan TV broadcasts 18 hours a day in analog and digital formats.

In April 2013, the Karakalpakstan TV channel was included in the digital broadcasting network. Due to the activities of the dubbing studio, which opened on June 1, 2013, young

viewers have the opportunity to watch cartoons in the Karakalpak language. In 2014, the second dubbing studio was launched, and movies and TV films began to be dubbed in Karakalpak. 95-98% of people in the Republic of Karakalpakstan watch Karakalpakstan TV. [1:82]

Goals and objectives of television, informing the public about the socio-political, socio-economic and material life of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, major social events, addressing issues of local government and self-government, socio-economic development, preparation of programs and radio broadcasts on the issues of increasing the political and social activity of citizens, the effective organization of their activities to protect their constitutional rights and freedoms. [2:92]

If we look at the history of Karakalpakstan radio, the archival materials prove that Karakalpakstan radio first started its activity on December 17, 1931 in Turtkul. By 1935, Karakalpakstan's radio broadcasts had reached three hours. During this period, rural life formed the content of the actual issues facing the people in the form of life. 1940 Radio Karakalpakstan is moved to Nukus. Until 1991, Karakalpakstan's broadcasts aired for 3.5 hours a day. Since 1993, the number of broadcasts has increased to 6.5 hours. These changes indicate the development of radio in Karakalpakstan. The archives of

Karakalpakstan Radio contain 800 hours of melodies and songs, 400 hours of radio staging, radio plays and performances. [3:99]

Conclusion

In conclusion, Karakalpakstan is making every effort to develop television and radio. Although the development of television and radio in Karakalpakstan began in the 1930s, it has not stopped. Television is important in our lives. Today's youth should learn the history of Karakalpakstan TV. It has a wonderful history. It is developing day by day. Animations have a great impact on the minds of young people. The Karakalpakstan TV team is doing well. The early history of radio is the history of technology that produces and uses radio instruments that use radio waves. Within the timeline of radio, many people contributed theory and inventions in what became radio. Radio development began as "wireless telegraphy". Later radio history increasingly involves matters of broadcasting. The meaning and usage of the word "radio" has developed in parallel with developments within the field of communications and can be seen to have three distinct phases: electromagnetic waves and experimentation; wireless communication and technical development; and radio broadcasting and commercialization. In 1886–88 Heinrich Rudolf Hertz conducted a series of experiments that proved the existence of Maxwell's electromagnetic waves, using a frequency in what would later be called the radio spectrum. Many individuals—inventors, engineers, developers and businessmen—constructed systems based on their own understanding of these and other phenomena, some predating Maxwell and Hertz's discoveries. Thus "wireless telegraphy" and radio wave-based systems can be attributed to multiple "inventors". Development from a laboratory demonstration to a commercial entity spanned several decades and required the efforts of many practitioners.

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